

DEVELOPING HUMAN RESOURCES FOR ETHNIC MINORITIES IN DAK LAK PROVINCE, VIETNAM

Pham Phuong Anh

PhD student,

University of Social Sciences and Humanities,

Vietnam

Vietnam National University Hochiminh city,

Vietnam

Abstract:

The issue of developing the human resources of ethnic minorities in Dak Lak province initially gains some remarkable achievements thanks to Vietnamese government's consideration. However, there are still several limitations such as low quality of human resources, unreasonable and inefficient exploitation and use of trained ethnic human resources. To meet the requirements of the current national renovation, human resources of ethnic minorities need to be paid more attention and invested. On the other hand, the human resources of ethnic minorities must constantly renew themselves. They have to be more proactive in apprenticeship, explore the labor market, look for jobs and form their industrial working style; they also need to avoid dependence, passivity, self-reliance and should not rely on the government as they used to. Through this article, we hope that it will make contribution to overcoming those limitations in the future.

Keywords: human resources, ethnic minorities, limitations, quality

1. Introduction

Dak Lak province is located in the center of the Central Highland, Vietnam. Its strategic position is particularly significant in economy, national defense and ecological environment in the Central Highland and the whole country. There are 47 ethnic groups in which 33% of them mainly reside in mountainous areas, whose lives are very difficult. In recent years, the ethnic and mountainous policies of the Party and State of Vietnam, which have been implemented in this province, have contributed to improving the physical and spiritual life of those ethnic people, especially ethnic minorities and mountainous area. However, there are populous ethnic minorities, mainly in remote areas in this region, there are still many challenges. Through this article, we appreciate the current situation of developing human resources in Dak Lak

province; thereby we give some basic solutions to develop ethnic human resources in Dak Lak province currently.

2. Content

2.1. Overview of ethnic minorities in Dak Lak province and Vietnam

In Dak Lak province, there are 47 ethnic groups accounting for about 33% of the whole provincial population, who live sparsely in 184 communes, wards and towns, in which ethnic minority households include Ede, M'ngong and J'rai people are local ethnic minorities, while other ethnic minorities migrate to this region such as Tay, Nung, Muong and Van Kieu, Dao, Thai, Hoa, Mong, and Ma etc. Most ethnic minorities retain their own cultural heritage, each of which draws a unique color in the whole colorful cultural life of the Central Highland. Although the local ethnic groups do not reside in separate regions, they often gather in a certain area. Ethnic minorities living in Dak Lak province often reside in center areas, some districts in the North and Northeast of the province, mainly in Buon Ma Thuot city. Those residents inhabit in different areas and follow matriarchy. Extended families live together in a long house and the community relations are maintained sustainably. The diversity of ethnic groups here has created a very unique culture.

2.2. Current situation of ethnic minority human resource development in Dak Lak province, Vietnam

When studying the current situation of human resources, we focus on issues such as quantity, quality and distribution. In term of the number of ethnic minority human resources in Dak Lak province is plentiful, the majority of labor is young people, the urban residents who tend to increase positively impact on the structure of labor resources, laborers and jobs. Although the number of ethnic human resources has seen positive changes during recent years, the issue of the number of human resources of the ethnic minorities in Dak Lak also remains some limitations such as the economic growth in relation to the increase in the number of human resources is inappropriate; human resources mainly inhabit in rural areas with low level of self-socio-economic development, production of self-sufficiency bases on an upland agricultural production. The educational level is low so the competence to access and acquire science, technology and new things is still limited. The number of laborers in the whole province accounts for 60.86%, of which the focus is mainly on agriculture and forestry (accounting for 66.94%), ethnic minority laborers makes up 32.81%. The population distribution on the region has not ensured sufficient human resources to exploit resources and effectively develop socio-economy. Untrained workers still account for a high proportion, while the rate of trained workers is low and has not met the requirements of socio-economic development and the process of industrialization and modernization; The physical indexes of ethnic minority human resources in Dak Lak province have had positive improvements in height and weight as well as health care for workers has been paid attention regularly etc... Thanks to the economic growth

process, the living standards of those people have changed progressively. Besides, together with the increase in the budget expense and the implementation of measures to prevent and control epidemics in ethnic minority and mountainous area, all of which have had good influences on the health state of human resources. The populous workforce with increasingly high level of expertise is the top requirement and a decisive factor for the success of the country's industrialization and modernization career.

In recent years, along with the development of physical index, the intellectual level and professional level of ethnic minority human resources in Dak Lak province have been increasingly raised due to the huge investment in education of the province. Students of ethnic minorities have had the opportunity to enter universities, colleges, professional secondary schools and vocational schools. The scale, network, system of schools and classes at all educational levels basically can meet the learning needs of ethnic children in the province and be suitable to the actual conditions of each commune, ward, district, city and the whole province. Currently, there are fourteen ethnic minority boarding schools in districts and cities (secondary school level) and one ethnic boarding high school – N' Trang Long high school – (upper secondary school). The system of boarding schools for ethnic minority students has been developed and has attracted more and more ethnic minority students. The development of teachers has been focused more and more.

However, illiteracy and re-illiteracy in some ethnic groups still account for a high proportion. By 2018, Dak Lak province has trained 18,119 ethnic minority laborers, which are classified according to the level of training as follows: Vocational college is 122 people; Vocational secondary level is 405 people; Primary vocational level is 3,375 people; continuing vocational training is 2,564 people. This is a really good premise for employees to improve their training level at higher levels of education. The distribution of human resources concentrates mainly in rural areas (76.82%) and they chiefly work in agriculture and rural areas; they are mostly untrained workers while the number of employees with professional qualifications and high skills is a minority. Although the economic restructuring in urban areas has been increasing in recent years, the quality of the labor force of ethnic minorities is still low and unable to meet the requirements and properties of the jobs which especially require a lot of knowledge.

Based on the research on the current development of ethnic minority human resources in Dak Lak province, we believe that the causes of the above limitations stem from the following issues; (1) The economic life of ethnic minorities is still low; production methods are small-scale and outdated; residential areas of ethnic minorities are complex with incomplete infrastructure and difficult economic exchanges between regions; (2) There is no link between the training and the employment of post-trained staff, which lead to the loss of trained human resources; (3) the influence of backward culture.

3. Discussion

From mastering viewpoints about human and human resources development of the Vietnamese government, we believe that in order to develop human resources in Dak Lak province next time, it is crucial to implement the following steps:

A. Firstly, developing human resources of ethnic minorities in Dak Lak province in the direction of allocating the labor force according to the local economic development planning, paying attention to job vacancies, promoting socio-economic background and stabilizing free migrants. Development of human resources of ethnic minorities in Dak Lak province now needs to be placed in the overall socio-economic development strategy. In Dak Lak province, ethnic minority human resources are still limited in terms of quality. Being a mountainous province with strengths and potentials in agriculture and forestry, there more than 70% of the population living in rural areas, laborers mainly work in agriculture, forestry and fisheries, in which workers are local ethnic minorities directly working in agricultural production. Therefore, restructuring of the economy towards production of goods for export and supply of raw materials for industry as well as promoting scientific and technical innovations in production to improve productivity, quality, competitiveness in the market are extremely essential. Those issues set challenges for the Party committees, authorities, organizations and ethnic minorities.

The laborers themselves, especially ethnic workers, are not fully aware of the importance of apprenticeship. They do not dare to participate and encourage their children to join vocational training. Their abilities to acquire knowledge and grasp vocational skills are limited. In Dak Lak province, there are a few of enterprises and the labor demands of those enterprises are not much. Also, a great deal of workers is afraid to go away from their families to work elsewhere. Many laborers participating in vocational training cannot support their life and their family well, so they do not have enough money to start up their own business. Therefore, the province authorities should pay attention to the jobs which are suitable to the expertise of current workers, especially the labor force working in the agricultural and rural production. They need to plan, organize and stabilize free migrants associating with the scheming of production areas to ensure that migrants have enough conditions to produce goods and improve their lives in all aspects. In addition, the authorities have to assure the security and national defense as well as promote the economy in ethnic minority areas.

B. Secondly, developing human resources of ethnic minorities in Dak Lak province require the province authorities to focus on comprehensively training and fostering the human resources, as well as raising the professional and labor skills, physical and ethical qualities of human resources. The authorities need to develop educational quality to be a key and comprehensive issue as well as pay attention to the training of human resources to meet the demands of the labor market in the province and region. They have to develop the scale and capacity of education and training networks which are capable of meeting the learning needs of people and the human resources of the provincial and regional socio-economic development. They should

implement policies on education development effectively as well as train the staff in rural and ethnic minorities areas, who are able to access science and technology and apply them to production and business. In addition, the authorities need to organize regularly vocational competitions for workers as regulations plus make a payment according to quantity and quality of products, all of which are to encourage employees to work hard, constantly improve their skills, manners and labor discipline.

C. Thirdly, developing human resources for ethnic minorities in Dak Lak province based on the awareness of position and role of human resources in the socio-economic development process. Focusing on socio-economic development, in which strong development and effective exploitation of ethnic human resources is the common goal of Dak Lak province. In order to successfully achieve the provincial goals, it is necessary to focus on the above human resources plus building essential socio-economic infrastructure and attracting investment capital as well as mobilizing enterprises and trades to actively participate in training human resources and employ qualified human resources effectively. In addition, it is indispensable to create an economic breakthrough in processing industry, high-tech agriculture, services and tourism together with preserving and promoting the rich and diverse national cultural identity.

The task of developing ethnic human resources is defined as one of the leading tasks of all leaders, which is concretized by the targets in the annual plan of each unit, department and province. It can be seen that the development of human resources for ethnic minorities not only is the responsibility of all levels and sectors, but also the entire task of the political system in the process of socio-economic development. Therefore, it is crucial to propagandize this issue throughout the political system and the whole society so that everyone can understand the policies on human resource development, the system of legal documents on labor, employment, education and training ..., all of which aim at making high consensus in the entire society.

4. Conclusion

In order to develop human resources of ethnic minority in Dak Lak province, Vietnamese government needs to create favorable conditions of housing and working for staff and students who graduated from universities, colleges and professional secondary schools are willing to work in ethnic minority areas and remote areas, especially for people who are ethnic people and highly qualified staff. In addition, the authorities ought to build, popularize and expand effective production models in villages and hamlets. Last but not least, they should promote the application of scientific and technological advances to increase productivity, production efficiency and raise income for laborers.

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